

THE HARMONY OF PEDAGOGICAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL RESEARCH IN THE FORMATION OF GEOECOLOGICAL CULTURE

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ABSTRACT. The article is devoted to the issues of interrelation and harmony of various disciplines in solving the scientific problem of forming geoeological culture, which is entering the field of modern scientific research, and is aimed at highlighting the points of contact between geographical and pedagogical research. It considers ecological culture as an integrative process. According to the author, the formation of geoeological culture is decided within the framework of pedagogical research, but he emphasizes that geoeology belongs to geography in terms of field, ecology in terms of direction, and geography in terms of subject and methodology. In this context, the importance of pedagogical conditions, ecological environment, geographical educational programs and didactic materials in the formation of geoeological culture is emphasized.

During the research of the topic, the available scientific literature and sources were reviewed from a critical and analytical perspective, and important pedagogical and geographical scientific conclusions on the formation of geoeological culture were summarized.

KEYWORDS: geoeological culture; geoeological education; geoeological educational environment, geoeological problem; sustainable development.

Introduction. In recent years, the issue of transforming geographical education into ecological education has become a topic of heated discussion by scientists, methodologists, and teachers in scientific publications and publicistic articles, and the topic of forming a geoeological culture has also become relevant. The main idea of the discussions was to emphasize that all concepts of geographical education have a general nature, pay more attention to the study of the geography of

one's own region, and are occupied with the formation of knowledge about ecological and geographical problems on the basis of local history. It is within the framework of these discussions that it seems appropriate to disclose ecological problems based on geographical knowledge. Thus, the ecologization of natural and geographical materials in the educational process helps to formulate questions that reveal the causes, intensity, and nature of anthropogenic impacts on natural complexes and natural phenomena. When studying them, schoolchildren learn that all components of natural complexes are inextricably linked with each other in a single system. Because the influence of one of the components inevitably leads to a change in the others.

The theoretical root of the need to ensure the harmony of pedagogical and geographical research in the formation of geoecological culture is associated with the fact that geoecological culture is considered as a method, process, measure and result of the cultural and historical development of the environment by man, adapting nature conservation activities for the sake of harmony and sustainable development of man with nature, understanding, and the cultivation of anthropogenically changed territories at various spatial levels. The measure of geoecological culture is a geoecological approach that involves the formation of human spiritual and moral qualities, the co-evolution of man and nature, and the preservation of ecological conditions and resources that are of ecological importance for present and future generations.

As is known, environmental education, as a new area of pedagogical theory and practice, appeared in scientific circles in the second half of the last century. Initially, it had the character of nature conservation education and was formed primarily as a branch of science related to the scientific understanding of the

problems of nature conservation and the increase of natural resources in science and society. The regulatory documents of that time emphasized the expediency of including the teaching of the basics of nature conservation in school programs and relevant sections of natural science, geography, and chemistry textbooks in order to teach young people respect for natural resources and the skills of proper use of natural resources. The theoretical foundations of the formation of schoolchildren's attitude to nature were developed in the studies of A. Zakhlebny, I. Zverev, L. Pechko, A. Sidelkovsky, I. Smolyaninov, I. Suravegina, and others.

Based on the ideas of ecological development, modern science, the strategy for developing ecological culture in the 21st century, and the strategic goal of ecologizing school geography, the categorical essence and methodological features of geoeological culture are determined as an advanced educational tool for sustainable development and given a modern description.

At the present stage of development of society, this issue is becoming more relevant, and the social necessity is being interpreted as the main goal of geographical and ecological education - the formation of an ecologically literate person. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to improve the tasks of ecologization and humanization of school education. This means not only the saturation of education with ecological, humanitarian and socially significant content, but also the formation and strengthening of an ecological and geographical culture, which includes a deep understanding of the interdependence and interdependence of man, society and nature.

The practical significance of the combination of pedagogical and geographical research in the formation of geoeological culture is due to the fact that the formation of geoeological culture is based on the cognitive model of geoeology in the

geographical, ecological, social (geocosocial) system as a method of studying the dialectics of human relations with the environment at various scales. It is also important that this process is a means of ensuring the unity of knowledge, coevolutionary value relations and creative activity of schoolchildren at the global, regional and local levels.

The emergence of geocological culture, its transformation into a subject of scientific research, is also the result of mankind's efforts to prevent, eliminate and reduce the risk of environmental problems. Indeed, in any interpretation, ecology can be discussed only from the point of view of living conditions in a specific geographical environment. The study of the interrelationship between society and the natural environment is the main direction of modern geographical research. The goals and objectives of geographical and environmental education are closely related to each other and have a special place in the formation of geocological culture. It is precisely in this context that the combination of geographical and pedagogical research can undoubtedly make a significant contribution to the solution of the issues of forming geocological culture as a scientific problem.

Sources and methods. In the research process, in addition to scientific sources on geocological culture, the legal and regulatory, curriculum and literature related to school environmental education in the republic's education system and its scientific paradigm aimed at the formation of geocological culture, as well as the results of experiments and tests conducted in regional schools, were studied using analysis, comparison, probability-statistics, and generalization methods.

Research results. The vital importance of the combination of pedagogical and geographical research in the formation of geocological culture lies in the fact that geocological culture is aimed at ensuring the formation of an integral quality

of the individual through school geography in the context of a modern culture-based model of environmental education and in the process of its ecologization. It is this process that ensures the socialization and self-development of the individual based on the ideals of sustainable development. Therefore, its activities correspond to the components and functions of ecological culture and are manifested as cognitive, axiological, normative, behavioral, creative and activity-related components associated with the cognitive, axiological and activity aspects of geocology.

That is, the result of the manifestation of geocological culture is geocological competence and spiritual and moral qualities of the individual, which contribute to the development of school geography in the context of the main goals of education for sustainable development. In addition, many scientists have emphasized that most environmental problems, with their biological priorities, go beyond classical ecology. They argue that complex geocological problems should come to the fore in the educational process. In this sense, it is recommended that geocological problems should become an integral organic part of all geographical courses.

Some studies describe the “geocological substructure” of ecological culture, that is, culture in the form of a substructure of the structure. In this regard, it is justified that geocological culture is a prerequisite for knowledge of nature, the implementation of environmentally rational and acceptable actions, and the enrichment of the content of activity with a value orientation, as well as the formation of a responsible attitude to the environment and the adoption of competent ecological decisions. This author also summarized and substantiated the logical structure of the content system of geocological education adapted to school education, including knowledge about the history of geocology, general

geoecology, global geoecology, landscape geoecology and methods of geoecological research. In our study, the concept of forming the geoecological culture of schoolchildren, developed on the basis of geography programs, taking into account the hierarchical levels of pedagogical research methodology, was studied in philosophical-methodological, scientific-theoretical, methodological, specific and methodological directions. Their review is given below:

The philosophical and methodological direction is represented by the ideas of ecological development, namely noospheregenesis, coevolutionary interaction, sustainable development. The culture of sustainable development is a new method and result of adapting and organizing human life. Ecological culture is the main culture of education for sustainable development. At the heart of its formation lie modern postulates of cultural and civilizational development, which include systematic, ecohumanistic, axiological tendencies.

In the theoretical and methodological direction, a set of hierarchically structured strategic approaches was mainly used. These are cultural-ecological, systemic-synergistic, ecological, axiological, spatial-temporal, problem-situational, personal-activity, cultural-competence, geoecological approaches. It is worth noting that here the geoecological approach reflects and implements the specific features of all higher-level approaches in the methodological system.

Also, a system of principles that implement strategic approaches, ensure the socialization of the individual, self-realization, and reflect the specific characteristics of geoecological culture was studied, namely, constructive and ecological activity and a spiritual and moral attitude to the world, the creation of a geoecological culture - the creation of an educational environment, natural and cultural harmony, dialogicity, cultural and historical continuity and ecological development,

knowledge of the problem situation, empathy and tolerance of interaction, ecological and creative activity, ecologization and integration, global-regional-local relations.

In the methodological direction, the process of forming geoeological culture of schoolchildren was considered within the framework of the methodological system of geography. In this regard, the following components were mainly studied:

- a target component reflecting the strategic goal of forming geoeological culture;
- an important component that implements a two-dimensional geoeological structure that reflects the external - components of geoeological culture and the internal - the specific nature of the individual;
- a procedural component reflecting the process of cultural development of personal and semantic dominants of the geoeological space, including cultural-adaptive, cultural-semantic, cultural-creative stages;
- a technological component aimed at creating situations of geoeological and cultural interaction;
- a performance-evaluation component that allows assessing the results of knowledge covering ecological aspects mastered by schoolchildren in geography, in accordance with the criteria developed for the formation of geoeological culture. This includes geoeological competence (motivational, value-normative, information-cognitive, communicative, practical-creative aspects) and human spiritual and moral qualities, especially such characteristics as empathy, tolerance, citizenship, and patriotism.

The specific and methodological direction consisted of a set of educational geoeological models (local, regional, global), which provided for the integration of geoeological content based on the ecologization of basic geography courses, step-

by-step geocological modules, integrated geocological courses, and integrated socially and personally significant forms of extracurricular activities in the activities of schoolchildren.

According to the results of our research, from the point of view of ensuring the harmony of pedagogical and geographical research in the formation of geocological culture, it would be appropriate to classify the methodological conditions for the formation of geocological culture of schoolchildren, the results of pedagogical analysis as follows:

1) geocological culture - creating a learning environment, awakening ecological feelings, organizing ecologically oriented meanings, systematically encouraging an ecological creative approach that ensures the sequence of forming geocological culture of schoolchildren;

2) interactive methods and forms aimed at the consistent formation of geocological competence and personal qualities in the context of the ideas of sustainable development, related to the types of geocological and cultural interaction situations;

3) the relationship between regular and extracurricular activities of schoolchildren, ensuring the socialization and self-development of the individual in the context of geocological culture for sustainable development;

4) methodological support (programs, textbooks, manuals) ensuring the effective formation of geocological culture.

The methodological conditions mentioned above are pedagogical tools aimed at determining the formation of geocological culture of schoolchildren through the curriculum of geography, and when creating a geocological educational

environment, they must be taken into account and form the basis of the content of the environment.

Conclusions and recommendations. Thus, geography and ecology are of great importance in the development of geocological thinking of a schoolchild. In addition, geography and ecology have great potential for educating students and shaping their worldview. Geography as a subject forms a system of scientific ecological and geographical knowledge, skills, views and beliefs that ensure the formation of civic responsibility of schoolchildren for the state of the environment. In this regard, the issue of harmonizing geographical, ecological and pedagogical research is of great scientific importance. Because it is precisely thanks to research and studies in this context that it will be possible to ensure the quality and effectiveness of work on the formation and development of geocological culture.

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